

Role of Behavioural Finance on Investment Decisions: A Comparative Study

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Abstract: Behavioural finance is an emerging concept that has a greater future scope. Behavioral finance can be defined as "the study of influence of psychology on the behaviour of investors and analysts". The behavioural finance says the impact of emotions, cognitive biases, and various psychological factors that drive the investment decision rather than traditional theories like human beings are rational. So this research intended to study the role of behavioural finance on investment decisions. This is a comparative study based on various demographic features. According to this study, each demographic feature may or may not be significantly different from the factors that influence the respondent's investment decision. We all know females are emotionally weaker than men. The attitude of women towards risk, return and Decision making criteria in investment selection are entirely different from men. The perception, attitude and psychology of women and men are too different. Age, education qualification, income level also have a greater impact on investment decisions. That makes more scope for this study. This study was conducted in Thrissur district. The research gave more focus on the factors which have an impact on investment decisions and also searches for how the investment decisions change due to various demographic features.

Introduction

Behavioural finance can be defined as "the study of influence of psychology on the behaviour of investors and analysts". It means the emotions, cognitive biases and various psychological factors that drive the investment decision rather than rational thinking. This research mainly focused on the impact or role of behavioural finance on investment decisions. The researcher intended to make a comparative study which helps to know how the demographic profile of people affects the investment decision. The behavioural finance theories expanded by numerous researchers, who spoke on gender and investment decisions. The gender predicament in investment decisions intently associated with behavioural finance. Moreover each demographic feature has an impact on investment decisions as well as the selection of investment avenues. The attitude, perception, learning level between gender groups or between age groups or between persons with different qualifications are distinct. So the main point that strikes on the mind of the researcher is that he is not rational about investments but he is judgemental because the emotions are most commonly influenced by his activities. The people may be orthodox or antagonistic, voluntary or involuntary, logical or illogical. Thus the researcher exhilarated to study the impact of various demographic features on investment decisions and to know the awareness level of respondents.

Statement of the Problem

The surging concept "behavioural finance" has a major role in investment decisions taken by each and every person. This study concerned "The

role of behavioural finance on investment decisions". The psychology, emotions, perceptions of different gender groups or in different age levels are distinct. Thus the researcher has made a comparative study. The use of income earned by each person uniquely. The fear about the future leads a person to set aside a certain part of income earned to meet unexpected events. So the researcher tries to study the various notions in behavioural finance and also its effect on investment decisions. The following are the research questions under consideration:

Q1: What are the factors influencing while making investment decisions?

Q2: Whether the respondents are aware about investment avenues?

Q3: How do demographic features impact investment decisions?

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the study.

To identify the factors which have an impact on investment decisions.

To know the awareness level of respondents regarding various investment avenues.

To discuss the impact of various demographic features on investment decisions.

Significance of the Study

Behavioural finance is an advancing contribution from the field of psychology which says emotions drive the action. This study is confined to consider the emotions, perceptions and attitude of investors from various demographic features and also contemplate the biases that are included in investment decisions. The attitudes of people are different by their gender, by their age or by education qualification. There is a lot

of research conducted by various researchers related to behavioural finance and it sticks to the gender differences in decisions. Thus the study focused on the impact of various demographic features on investment decisions. The role of behavioural finance in investment decisions has more scope in near future because the negative impact of Covid-19 on our economy and monetary transactions may last for a decade or more. Hence it is inevitable to conduct a study on the impact of behavioural finance on investment decisions.

Research Methodology

The research design is descriptive and analytical in nature. The data were collected from primary as well as secondary sources. The primary data were collected by administering questionnaires. Secondary data were collected from websites, Journals and magazines etc. The sample of the study was selected from Thrissur district. The researcher opted for 150 samples via convenience sampling.

Literature Review

Kannadas Sendivelu & Maniya Deepak Shah (2021) tries to find out the impact of behavioural finance on investment decisions of a single parent and Also assess the biases included in it.

Results & Discussion

The study concluded that every individual subjects to some biases.

Dhruv Sharma, Vandana Misra, J P Pathak (2021) tries to study the emergence of behavioural finance and the biases involved in it. The authors give focus on how behavioural finance supplemented the traditional finance theories by introducing behavioural aspects.

Rekha D M (2020) explored the behavioural determinants influencing investor's decisions and the level of influence of these factors on them. The study revealed that the prospect factors represent the most important factor having the highest significant impact on investment decisions.

Dr. Vinay Kandpal & Rajat Mehrotra(2018) attempts to study the behaviour of investors towards investment avenues and factors influencing while taking financial decisions. The study concludes that the behaviour have an huge impact while making wise decisions

Egidijus Bika, et al. (2013) explained the emergence and development of trends in behavioural finance. This research revealed the aims of recognition and emotional factors focusing on a limited number of rational investors.

Table No: 1, Demographic Profile

	Frequency	Percent
Gender		
Male	78	52
Female	72	48
Total	150	100
Age		
20-30	17	11.33
30-40	72	48
40-50	40	26.67
50-60	13	8.67
Above 60	8	5.33
Total	150	100
Monthly Income		
Below 20000	76	50.67
20000-40000	38	25.33

40000-60000	24	16
Above 60000	12	8
Total	150	100
Education		
Below SSLC	18	12
SSLC	30	20
Plus two	34	22.67
Graduate	22	14.67
Post Graduate	18	12
Others	28	18.66
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The demographic table depicts that 52 percent of respondents are male. 48 percent of respondents are coming under the age group of 30-40. Most of the respondents nearly

50.67 percent earned an income up to 20000. Most of the respondents have a minimum plus two qualifications.

Table No: 2, Awareness about behavioural finance

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Aware	134	89.33
Not aware	16	10.67
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the table it is clear that around 90 percent of respondents have heard about the emerging concept behavioural finance.

Table No: 3, Influence of behavioural finance on investment decision

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Always	49	32.67
Often	32	21.33
Sometimes	26	17.33
Rarely	27	18
Never	16	10.67
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The tables depicts the influence of behavioural finance on investment decisions. 32.67 percent are always influenced by

behavioural factors and 10.67 percent of them are not influenced and not aware about that.

Hypothesis 1

H0: There is no significant difference between male and female regarding the influence of behavioral finance on investment decisions.

H1: There is a significant difference between male and female regarding the influence of behavioral finance on investment decisions.

Table No. : 4, Gender wise - Mann - Whitney - Wilcoxon U - Test

	Gender	N	Test statistic	Table value@ 5%	P value	Accept/ Reject
Influence of behavioural finance	Male	78	10.5	2	-0.31334	Reject
	Female	72				
Test distribution is not normal Mann - Whitney - Wilcoxon U - Test Grouping Variable: Gender						

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The table depicts the calculated value greater than table value at 5% level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected

and it means there is a significant difference between the influences of behavioural finance on gender groups.

Table No: 5, Awareness about investment avenues

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Extremely aware	52	34.67
Moderately aware	56	37.33
Somewhat aware	26	17.33
Slightly aware	16	10.66
Not at all aware	0	0
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the table it is clear that all the respondents are aware about the investment avenues in distinct ways. 37.33 percent of respondents are moderately aware about all kinds of investment avenues.

H0: There is no significant difference between male and female regarding awareness about investment avenues.

H1: There is a significant difference between male and female regarding awareness about investment avenues.

Hypothesis 2

Table No. : 6, Gender wise T test

	Gender	N	Test statistic	Table value@ 5%	Accept/ Reject
Awareness regarding investment avenues	Male	78	2.63	1.96	Reject
	Female	72			
Test distribution is normal T test Grouping Variable: Gender					

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the table it is clear that the test statistic is greater than the critical value at 5% level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected that the male and female get awareness in different ways.

Hypothesis 3

H0: There is no significant difference between age and awareness about investment avenues

H1: There is significant difference between age and awareness about investment avenues

Table No.: 7, Age wise – kruskal- wallis H test

	Age	N	Test statistic	Table value@ 5%	Accept/ Reject
Awareness level	20-30	17	6.524	9.488	Accept
	30-40	72			
	40-50	40			
	50-60	13			
	Above 60	8			
	Total	150			

Test distribution is not normal
Kruskal Wallis H Test
Grouping Variable: Age

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the table it is clear that the calculated value is less than table value. Hence we accept the null hypothesis. That means there is no significant difference between age groups and the awareness of investment avenues.

H0: There is no significant difference between male and female regarding awareness level of individual investment avenues.

H1: There is a significant difference between male and female regarding the awareness level of individual investment avenues.

Hypothesis 4

Table No.: 8, Awareness on individual investment avenues

Investment Avenue	Gender	No.	Mean	Standard Deviation	Calculated Value	Table Value	Accept/Reject
Bank Deposit	Male	39	4.025	.973	.671	1.96	Accept
	Female	36	3.88	.9038			
Post Office Savings	Male	39	3.71	.987	-3.58	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	7.416	6.135			
Insurance	Male	39	4.076	1.04	2.51	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	3.416	1.21			
Share	Male	39	2.79	1.38	2.30	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	2.11	1.17			
Bonds/ Debentures	Male	39	2.74	1.34	2.43	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	2.05	1.10			
Chit Fund	Male	39	4.23	.894	2.63	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	3.66	.97			
Real Estate	Male	39	3.66	1.43	4.18	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	2.5	.92			
Provident Fund	Male	39	3.897	1.23	2.6	1.96	Reject
	Female	36	3.11	1.35			

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: While considering post office savings, insurance, shares, bonds, chit funds, real estate, and provident fund, according to t-test calculated values are more than the table value, so reject the null hypothesis and accept the

alternative hypothesis that is awareness level of respondents towards various investment avenues are significantly differ in between male and female.

Table No: 9
Sources of awareness

Source	Frequency	Percent
News paper	40	26.67
Television	34	22.67
Friends or colleagues	24	16
Brokers or consultants	18	12
Journals or magazines	12	8
E- sources	22	14.66
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The table shows that 26.67 percent of respondents get awareness about investment avenues through newspapers or

dailies. Least of the respondents get the information from journals or magazines.

Table No: 10
Decision taken on investment

Variable	Frequency	Percent
Independently	27	18
Friends	41	27.33
Family members	38	25.33
Neighbors	15	10
Brokers and consultants	17	11.34
Others	12	8
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The above table depicts that most of the respondents are taking decisions

regarding investment by considering the words of friends, family members or by individually.

Table No: 11, Income set aside for investment

Category	Frequency	Percent
0-25%	79	52.67
25-50%	60	40
50-75%	11	7.33
More than 75%	0	0
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the table it is clear that 53 percent of respondents are keeping less than 25% of income for investment and none of them keep more than 75% of income for investments.

Table No: 12
Variables control the investment decision

Variables	Frequency	Percent
Confidence to invest	28	18.67
Regular review and comparison	7	4.67
Consistent investment strategy	13	8.67
Knowledge about avenues	36	24
Satisfaction with current investment avenues	10	6.66
Risk bearing capacity	32	21.33
Possible returns	24	16
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the table it is clear that 24 percent of respondents are considering knowledge about avenues as a control variable. Least controlling variable is regular review and comparison about 5 percent.

Table No: 13
Investment avenues preferred

Investment Avenues	Frequency	Percentage
Bank Deposit	42	28
Post Office Savings	30	20
Insurance	20	13.3
Shares	6	4
Bonds/Debentures	10	6.7
Chit Funds	26	17.33
Real Estate	0	0
Provident Fund	16	10.7
Total	150	100

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The above table mentions that most of the respondents opt bank deposits, post office savings and chit funds as preferred investment avenues. Because these three avenues have the least level of risk and most of the respondents have risk averse character.

Table No: 14
Factors considering while making investment decisions

Attributes	Frequency	Percentage
Assured return	130	86.7
Tax benefits	142	94.7
Child education	86	57.3
Daughters marriage	52	34.7
Speculation	33	22.0
Capital gain	21	14.0
Retirement benefit	79	52.7
Secured future	111	74.
Safety of investment	148	98.7
Quantum of investment	127	84.7
Potential risk	150	100
Potential gain	56	37.3
Liquidity	67	44.7
Customer service	31	20.7
Past experience	133	88.7
Time horizon	47	31.3

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: The table shows that the most concerning factors while making investment decisions are potential risk, safety of investment and assured return. The least affected factor is the capital gain earned from the investments.

Hypothesis 5

H0: There is no significant difference between male and female regarding the factors considered for making investment decisions.

H1: There is a significant difference between male and female regarding the factors considered for making investment decisions.

Table No: 15
Genderwise - Mann - Whitney - Wilcoxon U - Test

Factors	Male (N ₁)	Female (N ₂)	Test statistic	Table value@ 5%	Accept/ Reject
Assured return	58	72	96.5	75	Reject
Tax benefits	70	72			
Child education	20	66			

Daughters marriage	8	44			
Speculation	29	4			
Capital gain	18	3			
Retirement benefit	7	72			
Secured future	41	70			
Safety of investment	76	72			
Quantum of investment	57	70			
Potential risk	78	72			
Potential gain	50	6			
Liquidity	13	54			
Customer service	4	27			
Past experience	61	72			
Time horizon	13	34			
Total	603	810			
a) The distribution is not normal b) Mann – Whitney – Wilcoxon U test c) Grouping Variable : Gender					

(Source: Primary Survey)

Interpretation: From the above calculations it is clear that the test statistic is greater than the critical value. Hence we reject the null hypothesis which means there is a significant difference between male and female regarding the factors considering for investment decisions

Findings

The following are the major findings of the study.

52 percent of respondents are male. 48 percent of respondents are coming under the age group of 30-40. Most of the respondents nearly 50.67 percent earned an income up to 20000. Most of the respondents have a minimum plus two qualifications.

90 percent of respondents have heard about the emerging concept of behavioural finance.

32.67 percent are always influenced by behavioural factors and 10.67 percent of them are not influenced and not aware about that.

There is a significant difference between the influences of behavioural finance on gender groups.

All the respondents are aware about the investment avenues in distinct ways. 37.33 percent of respondents are moderately aware.

There is a significant difference between male and female on the awareness regarding investment avenues.

There is no significant difference between age groups and the awareness of investment avenues. While considering post office savings, insurance, shares, bonds, chit funds, real estate, and provident fund, according to t-test calculated values are more than the table value, so reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis that is awareness level of respondents towards various investment avenues are significantly differ in between male and female. 26.67 percent of respondents get awareness about investment avenues through newspapers or dailies.

Most of the respondents are taking decisions regarding investment by considering the words of friends, family members or individually.

53 percent of respondents are keeping less than 25% of income for investment and none of them keep more than 75% of income for investments.

24 percent of respondents are considering knowledge about avenues as a control variable.

Most of the respondents opt bank deposits, post office savings and chit funds as preferred investment avenues. Because these three avenues

have the least level of risk and most of the respondents have risk averse character.

Most concerning factors while making investment decisions are potential risk, safety of investment and assured return.

There is a significant difference between male and female regarding the factors considered for investment decisions.

Suggestions

Following are the suggestions derived from the study.

The female investors should be encouraged to invest since they are very cautious about the avenues, risk and return.

The Government Should take initiatives to give adequate training programs to people with less literacy level.

Government should arrange awareness programs to the entire public to encourage them to create investment behaviour.

Respondents should take due care while making investment decisions.

Most of the respondents are ready to save their income rather than investing in risky avenues. So the concerned authorities should take initiatives to encourage the public for investment.

Conclusion

The researcher tried to compare the role of behavioural finance on investment decisions based on some demographic features like gender and age. From the study it is clear that almost all respondents opted for savings rather than investment. Because they regret taking the risk. The female respondents are not interested in investing in risky avenues and also they do not expect more earnings. The female respondents used the investment or savings for the future rather than male invest for making immediate return. They are not cautious about the future unlike females. All the respondents are aware about the investment avenues but distinctly. Most of the respondents opt bank deposits, post office savings and chit funds as preferred investment avenues. Because these three avenues have the least level of risk and most of the respondents have risk averse character. The study was entirely conducted in the rural area of Thrissur district. So the respondents have not much idea regarding investment in shares, debentures as such investments. Thus the authorities should take initiatives for educating the rural people about investment avenues. There is a significant difference between male and females regarding the factors influenced while making investment decisions. The investment behaviour of

respondents are changed according to the variations in demographic features.

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